

On the use of non-destructive testing for the measurement of self-healing in lime-based mortars

Franco Grosso Giordano^{a,b,*}, Maxime Brunin^b, Nico Boon^a, Nele De Belie^b

^aGhent University, Center for Microbial Ecology and Technology (CMET), Coupure Links 653, B-9000 Ghent, Belgium

^bGhent University, Magnel-Vandepitte Laboratory, Dept. of Structural Engineering and Building Materials, Technologiepark Zwijnaarde 60, B-9052, Ghent, Belgium

Abstract

The study of self-healing construction materials has increased in popularity over the last couple of decades. Nevertheless, most research has predominantly focused on cement-based materials and work on other type of binders such as lime-based mortars remains rather limited. Despite the multiple testing methods available to assess the efficacy of self-healing, these techniques are not always suitable for materials of different mechanical strengths and behavior. In order to further expand the knowledge on self-healing beyond the high-strength cement-based materials, self-healing has been studied on low-strength binders. Here it is shown how the use of non-destructive testing with ultrasonic pulse velocity (UPV) can help determine the self-healing capacity of low-strength mortars. A hydrated-lime:metakaolin mortar mix and cement mix were cast and damaged after 7 days of curing. The samples were damaged under compression using 70 % of the average compressive strength. Before and after damaging, the samples were tested by UPV and superficial cracks were studied by microscopy. The samples were then placed under wet-dry cycles of 1 hour wet/23 hours dry or submersion for 28 days and tested again. As healing proceeded, an increase in the UPV was observed. Microscopy measurements confirmed visually the self-healing of cracks in all samples. The mechanical strength of both formulations was similar after healing when compared to a non-damaged and non-healed sample. These results show the necessity for techniques that are tailored to the mechanical nature of the different studied materials and opens up the possibility of further investigating self-healing in a wider variety of construction materials.

Keywords: Self-healing; lime-based, mortars; non-destructive; ultrasonic pulse velocity;

1. Introduction

Lime is the oldest known cementitious material dating back over 9000 years [1]. On top of that, its role as a healing agent has been known and harnessed for at least 2000 years [2]. Yet, it has received little attention in the field of self-healing materials with most research focusing on cements [3–5]. Nonetheless, it has recently come into the spotlight as a potential substitute for cement due to its lower carbon footprint. Its capacity to react with atmospheric CO₂ as it hardens has made it a potential carbon sink during the life span of cement structures.

Yet, most hydrated-lime mortar formulations have different mechanical properties, particularly they are of lower strength than those which are predominantly cement based. A lime mortar for masonry is usually not tested for mechanical properties before 28 days of curing [6] and have a compressive strength range of 2 – 15 MPa [7]. Conversely, cement mortars can have strengths that vary from 32 – 62 MPa in the same time span [8]. As such, lime-based mortars lend themselves to a very different handling than cementitious materials. This means they need different methods of testing. Furthermore, these stark differences in mechanical properties imply that lime-based mortars are used in different scenarios to cement mortars. For this it is important to adapt testing techniques more applicable to their real-work applications. While cement is used ubiquitously in construction, lime-based mortars see a major role in masonry structures under compressive forces.

For this purpose, the possibility of testing self-healing in lime-based mortars is studied through previously used non-destructive techniques, specifically ultrasonic pulse velocity. Ultrasonic pulse velocity (UPV) is a standard technique for the study of concrete elasticity and density. Pulses of longitudinal stress waves are sent from a transmitting transducer to a receiver and the time taken for this propagation is measured. These values can then be used to evaluate the uniformity and relative quality of a concrete, changes in the properties of the concrete and indicate presence of cracks [9] as the propagation of ultrasonic waves through the material will change according to the density of the material. For testing propagation, as more cracks form in the cementitious matrix, there is an increase within the

* Corresponding author. E-mail address: franco.grossogiordano@ugent.be

air space of the region of interest. As the waves cannot traverse these phases, the wave is forced to travel further to get past the crack and as such the signal takes longer to reach the receiver [10]. Yet, as the cracks begin to heal, the time taken by the wave reduces as the wave takes a straighter trajectory to the receiver. This principle has been used to test self-healing before with success [11, 12]. Nevertheless, there are some shortcomings of UPV such as the required consistency of application by the operator and the coupling of the transducers to the sample surface (ATSM-C597-16).

It is also important to have an observable record of the healing process. For this, microscopy is used on superficial cracks to determine if the recorded changes in UPV are also measurable at the crack surface. Microscopy has been universally used to study self-healing in the past. Secondly, although the return of the UPV of the damaged samples to the undamaged state is an indication of healing, it is hard to quantify the extent of regain in mechanical properties. For this reason, regain in mechanical strength will be tested after 28 days of curing.

The mixes were 2:1:9 hydrated-lime:metakaolin:aggregate mortar and 1:3 cement:aggregate volume ratio mixes and were damaged after 7 days of curing (LMK7 and C7, respectively). UPV was measured on the undamaged samples and samples damaged under compressive loading. Microscopy was used to observe surface cracks on damaged samples. The damaged samples were placed under two healing regimes, 1 hour wet – 23 hours dry cycles and full submersion under water, for 28 days. After 28 days samples were tested for UPV and microscopy again and cracked until failure.

2. Methodology

2.1. Mortar formulations and sample preparation

Hydrated-lime (CL 90-S, Lhoist), metakaolin (Metapor, PORAVÉR) and a cement (CEM-II AL, Tarmac) were used to prepare the mortars. A binder:aggregate volume ratio of 1:3 was used for the mortars, with the lime:metakaolin binder ratio being 2:1. The water/binder ratio was determined according to EN 1015-2, to achieve a flow value of 165 ± 3 mm or 175 ± 5 mm for the lime-metakaolin or cement mix, respectively. Casting was performed as per EN 1015-11, with the exception that the gauze and filter paper were placed on only the upper side of the lime-metakaolin mortar due to mould limitations. The samples were cast in $50 \times 50 \times 50$ mm³ moulds. The mould could be completely taken apart to prevent causing prestress to the soft lime samples when demoulding.

2.2. Damage and self-healing conditions

A total of twelve samples were prepared to be tested at 7 days after casting. Three samples were tested under compression until failure to get the compressive strength of the mortar at 7 days. Six more samples were then damaged to 70 % of the failure strength. Three damaged samples were placed 1 hour under water – 23 hours in standard curing conditions (SDC, 65 % relative humidity and 20 °C) and three damaged samples were placed under submersion in water. Three more samples were left in SDC to test the strength of mortars after 28 days unaffected by healing regimes. Tap water was used in both cases.

2.3. Ultrasonic Pulse Velocity

A 55 Hz transmitting transducer was used. Before testing, samples were placed for 24 in SDC to minimize the effect of water on the measurements. The sample was mounted on a wooden stand and the transducers were placed on both ends of the sample on wooden stands. Vaseline was used as a coupling agent between the sample and the transducers which were pressed against the sample. All samples were measured at the center point of the cube, in the direction of the damage. All three samples were measured in three locations across the surface. UPV was measured on 7 days old samples before (D0) and after damage (D0dam). The date at which samples were placed in healing regimes, marks the starting point of the experiment (D0). Samples were placed in healing conditions and the evolution of healing was monitored after 7 (D7) and 28 days (D28) of healing.

2.4. Calculations

The following parameters could be calculated based on the measurements taken:

- 1) The damage coefficient (DC) or the loss of UPV due to the damage on the sample:

$$DC = \frac{D0 - D0dam}{D0} \times 100 (\%) \quad (1)$$

2) The healing coefficient (HC) or the regain in UPV due to healing at the different time points measured:

$$HC = \frac{D(7 \text{ or } 28) - D0dam}{D0 - D0dam} \times 100 (\%) \quad (2)$$

For both equations, $D0$, $D0dam$, $D7$ and $D28$ are the values of UPV at the measured dates.

2.5. Microscopy

Crack widths were observed for healing using an optical microscope (Leica DMC 2900) and images were taken at $D0dam$ and $D28$.

2.6. Regain in compressive strength

At $D28$, after all non-destructive testing, compressive strength tests until failure were performed on all samples to calculate the regain in compressive strength of the material. Although UPV and microscopy provide indications of the extent of crack self-healing, they do not provide an indication on the regain in mechanical and durability properties of the material. A regain in compressive strength, the main force that mortars experience in a masonry structure, thus provides evidence of the regain in functionality.

3. Results

3.1. Ultrasonic Pulse Velocity

The use of UPV on LMK7 posed some practical implications due to the low cohesion of the material. Primarily, the use of vaseline to improve the coupling of the sensors to the cube was difficult to remove from the materials. It could lead to the detachment of material from the sample. Also in the process, the roughness of LMK7 compared to the smoother surfaces of C7 implied that the coupling of the material was not always ideal. Lastly, maintaining a good coupling was delicate as applying too much pressure on to the mortar could result in unwanted damage. Three measurements per sample were used to achieve a more robust measurement.

Overall, UPV showed similar trends for LMK7 and C7 (Figure 1). When the sample has been damaged under compression ($D0dam$), there is a sharp decrease in the UPV for all samples, while as healing proceeds we observe a regain in UPV. This is quantified using the calculated DC and HC which provide a magnitude of the damage and healing in percentage. DC values are expected to be < 100 otherwise the sample has been completely destroyed, Meanwhile, values of $HC = 100$ indicate a complete return to the $D0$ UPV values, values of $HC > 100$ show an increase beyond the $D0$ UPV values, and $HC < 100$ show that healing has not achieved $D0$ levels.

The DC on average is higher for C7 than LMK7 (Table 1). Then, as samples are placed in the healing regimes ($D7$ and $D28$), a gradual increase to the original UPV was measured. All LMK7 achieve and surpass their non-damaged UPV ($HC > 100$) within 7 days of healing in both regimes (Figure 1 bottom and Table 1). One C7 sample (sample 2, Submersion regime) returned to pre-damage UPV within 7 days and two samples under submersion had a $HC > 100$ after 28 days (Figure 1 top and Table 1).

Furthermore, the HC measured with UPV varies per regime (Table 1). C7 samples healed significantly better under submersion which almost doubled the HC of water cycles. Meanwhile, LMK7 seems to favor water cycles although the difference is not significant. In all cases, the $HC28$ was higher than the $HC7$.

Table 1. Values of UPV DC, HC7 and HC28 for C7 and LMK7 samples. Individual sample and average values are shown for both healing regimes. All values in %.

Sample	C7			LMK7		
	DC	HC7	HC28	DC	HC7	HC28
Water cycles 1	31.7	24.4	52.8	20.1	128.1	222.0
Water cycles 2	28.6	25.1	42.7	10.4	188.9	409.7
Water cycles 2	38.0	34.5	53.9	14.7	151.9	265.3
Average	32.8	28.0	49.8	15.1	156.3	299.0
Std dev	3.9	4.6	5.0	4.0	25.0	80.3
Submersion 1	14.1	76.5	123.0	15.4	166.8	256.3
Submersion 2	14.6	101.2	119.9	15.6	137.7	276.9
Submersion 3	31.5	41.7	65.5	27.7	missing	121.4
Average	20.0	73.2	102.8	19.6	152.3	218.2
Std dev	8.1	24.4	26.4	5.8	NA	69.0

Evolution of UPV of cement samples damaged at age 7

Evolution of UPV of lime-metakaolin samples damaged at age 7

Figure 1. UPV (m/s) measurements of C7 (top) and LMK7 (bottom) samples at the damage age of 7 days. Mean UPV is shown. Three measurements were performed per measurement on each sample.

3.2. Microscopy

In order to have physical evidence of healing, cracks were photographed after damage and at the end of the healing period of 28 days. LMK7 did not see healing (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Microscopy images for C7 and LMK7 at D0dam and D28. Scale bar of 500 μm applies to all images.

3.3. Compressive strength of the binder mixes and regain in strength

C7 samples provided a high strength comparison to the lower strength LMK7 samples. The compressive strengths were $23.9 \pm 0.8 \text{ N/mm}^2$ and $0.66 \pm 0.09 \text{ N/mm}^2$ respectively (Table 2).

A control that was undamaged and untreated in either regime of C7 and LMK7 was used to compare the regain in strength of damaged samples to a non-damage scenario. Only LMK7 achieved a strength higher than non-damaged samples cured in SDC, with up to 11 % more strength achieved with water cycles, although the difference was not significant. C7 was on average lower than the undamaged sample but also not significantly different.

Table 2. Compressive strength values for C7 and LMK7 at start (D0) and after healing period (D28) in the different healing regimes. 3 samples were kept in SDC to measure the normal gain in strength over time.

Binder	Strength at start (D0) (N/mm^2)	Damage force (kN)	Regime	Final strength after healing period (D28) (N/mm^2)
C7	23.9 ± 0.8	26.8	Water cycles	21.25 ± 0.88
			Submersion	22.02 ± 1.07
			No damage and no treatment	23.28 ± 2.57
LMK7	0.66 ± 0.09	1.2	Water cycles	0.59 ± 0.07
			Submersion	0.55 ± 0.07
			No damage and no treatment	0.53 ± 0.09

4. Discussion

The main aim of this paper was to adapt non-destructive techniques to monitor self-healing in low-strength binders. C7 provided a control as UPV have been used in cementitious materials in the past [11]. LMK7, on the other hand,

was used as a low-strength binder. The range of strengths was high between both mixes, as they had a strength of $23.9 \pm 0.8 \text{ N/mm}^2$ for C7 and $0.66 \pm 0.09 \text{ N/mm}^2$ for LMK7.

Overall, UPV provided similar results in the low-strength mortar as it did for high strength. Still, some differences were observed. On LMK7 samples, the DC is lower than that of C7 samples on average. This could imply the damaged exerted on the former created less extensive crack networks, which is shown by the fact that surface cracks identified microscopically on LMK7 were smaller. Due to the softness of LMK7 and its higher malleability, it is hypothesized that upon compression, the pore network is being compressed, leading to a compensation of UPV when the cracks are being formed. Furthermore, UPV discerned clear differences between the tested healing regimes, where it seems that submersion led to better healing in C7 samples. The average HC28 of C7 samples under water cycles was 49.8 % vs that of 102.8 % under submersion.

The use of mechanical strength test to measure the development of strength during healing coincides with UPV results. In both mortars and both healing regimes, we observe comparable strength to samples that were undamaged and not placed in the different healing regimes. Still, it is good to use this technique in combination with non-destructive testing as it cannot provide a value for the healing capacity of the sample since it is not possible to test the full compressive strength of the sample after damage if the sample is to be used for further testing.

Despite that lime mortar is one of the oldest described construction materials to undergo self-healing [12,13], research on self-healing in low-strength binders such as lime is still limited [14]. A recent rise in interest in lime-based mortars has led to an advancement in the field, yet it remains in its infancy when compared to cement based mortars and concretes. Given the mechanical differences observed between cement and low-strength binders such as lime mortar, techniques need to be adapted to the latter binder systems. The present work helps towards exploring methodologies suitable for lower strength binders, showing how UPV offers the possibility to discretely monitor the progress of healing throughout the experimental campaign.

A need for adaptations was observed for both techniques. With regards to the limitations of using UPV in this experimental campaign, the high dependency on the operator could mean that results might vary from experiment to experiment. For this, testing in a fixed setup with a locking mechanism is proposed, allowing to take subsequent measurements on exactly the same location and with the same pressure on the sensors. Through this, it is also possible to prevent any damage to the sample by application of too much pressure on the mortar specimens. Also, the amount of handling, including the application of a coupling agent, can damage mortars with low cohesion which requires extra care when testing. Nevertheless, its application in two different types of binders has been shown.

Meanwhile, compressive strength tests cannot be used in a recurring manner during an experimental campaign to measure progress of healing, unless large number of specimens are prepared per series.

Complementary techniques to UPV and compressive strength tests should be further explored. Some non-destructive tests used previously in cement-based mortars and concretes to be evaluated in the context of low-strength binders include resonant frequency [13], μCT [14] and water permeability tests [15].

5. Conclusion

Overall, the use of UPV, regain in compressive strength and microscopy provide a comprehensive indication of the self-healing of the mortars tested. UPV seems accurate as a non-destructive technique for the measurement of self-healing in low-strength binders. Still, UPV has some impracticalities associated to the extra handling of the materials that could lead to damages or total loss of samples.

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